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Burkina Faso: a country with exceptional tourism potential

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ABSTRACT

Burkina Faso is a country in West Africa. It straddles the Sahelian and Sudanese zones. This gives the north and centre of the country an arid, steppe-like climate. In contrast, the south is dominated by a tropical climate and savannah. This results in exceptional landscape diversity. The country is home to more than a dozen ethnic groups, each with their own unique culture. This article attempts to showcase the unique landscapes and cultures of Burkina Faso's peoples. However, tourism has recently been affected by terrorist attacks, particularly in the north and east of the country.

Keywords: Burkina Faso, landscape diversity, tourism, geography

INTRODUCTION

Upper Volta, the colonial name for Burkina Faso, was created in 1919. During the colonial period, many Mossi people fought in World War I as Senegalese riflemen. In 1932, Upper Volta was abolished as a colony and divided among other French territories, before being reconstituted in 1947. Upper Volta joined the French Community in 1958 and gained independence on August 5, 1960. In 1984, under the revolutionary presidency of Thomas Sankara, Upper Volta was renamed Burkina Faso, meaning “land of honest men.” Thomas Sankara pursued a policy of national emancipation, development, and the fight against corruption until his death in 1987. Since then, the country has seen several regimes, including that of Blaise Compaoré (1987-2014) and recent presidencies such as that of Roch Marc Christian Kaboré. Today, Burkina Faso is under a progressive revolutionary regime led by President Ibrahim Traoré. The country has been facing terrorism since 2015, which is being defeated as various terrorist attacks decline (see Maps 1 & 2) [1-6].

Burkina Faso's tourism potential is characterized by its impressive cultural richness and natural diversity, which attract a growing number of tourists. The country is renowned for its diverse environments, including natural parks teeming with flora and fauna, multicultural sites and unique landscapes. Three tourist areas have been identified (see Map 3).

Climate diversity has resulted in a variety of landscapes. Burkina Faso has experienced extreme weather conditions for several decades [7-12], leading to the emergence of exceptional landscapes in both the arid and steppe zones (**Photos 1-7**) and the tropical and savanna zones (**Photos 8-12**), which have been shaped by water and wind erosion over hundreds of years.

The physical environment, particularly the rocks, offers open-air museums throughout the country. In the Ziniaré area of Loango, there is a locality home to granite rocks sculpted by artists over several years. This makes the Loango area a unique tourist destination (**Photos 13-32**) (Symposium de sculpture sur granit de Laongo). Several waterfalls can be seen in Banfora in the west of the country (**Photos 33-36**). Burkina Faso also boasts a wide variety of birds and animals in parks throughout the country (**Photos 37-50**) [13-24].

Several ethnic groups coexist within the country [25-30]. This has resulted in unusual architecture, such as the Kassena houses (**Photos 51-53**). Additionally, several ethnic groups in western Burkina Faso produce pottery that attracts tourists (**Photos 54-61**). A variety of dances are also performed by the different ethnic groups (**Photos 62-79**).

Map 1. Location of country in Africa – Burkina Faso (Google).

Map 2. Burkina Faso (Google).

Map 3. Diversity of tourist areas in Burkina Faso.

The main socioeconomic activities in rural areas are agriculture (**Photos 80-84**), industrial mining, and gold panning (**Photos 85-87**). Burkina Faso has several cities, including Ouagadougou, Bobo-Dioulasso, Koudougou, and Houndé (**Photos 88-93**).

CONCLUSIONS

The country contains over sixty popular tourist sites, including the granite sculptures of Laongo, which attract thousands of visitors each year. It is divided into four major tourist areas: the east, which has large natural parks; the Sahel in the north, which has pre-desert landscapes and an authentic culture; the center, which has Ouagadougou and its business and cultural tourism; and the west, which has rich but underdeveloped ethnic diversity. The western region has around 216 tourist sites, 96 of which are considered to be of major interest. However, the region still suffers from a lack of infrastructure and adequate tourism development.

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Appendix

Photo 1. Landscape shaped by erosion in Boromo, (Photograph by Yaméogo Joseph, 2022).

Photo 2. Eroded soil in Boromo, (Photograph by Yaméogo Joseph, 2022).

Photo 3. Landscape shaped by erosion in Boromo, (Photograph by Yaméogo Joseph, 2022).

Photo 4. Landscape shaped by erosion in Boromo, (Photograph by Yaméogo Joseph, 2022).

Photo 5. Landscape shaped by erosion in Boromo, (Photograph by Yaméogo Joseph, 2022).

Photo 6. Landscape shaped by erosion in Boromo, (Photograph by Yaméogo Joseph, 2022).

Photo 7. Landscape shaped by erosion in Boromo, (Photograph by Yaméogo Joseph, 2022).

Photo 8. Sindou peaks shaped by erosion, source: ONTB.

Photo 9. Landscape shaped by erosion in Sindou, source: ONTB.

Photo 10. Sindou peaks shaped by erosion, source: ONTB.

Photo 11. Sindou peaks shaped by erosion, source: ONTB.

Photo 12. Sindou peaks shaped by erosion, source: ONTB.

Photo 13. Laongo, an open-air sculpture museum,
(Symposium de sculpture sur granit de Laongo).

Photo 14. Laongo, an open-air sculpture museum,
(Symposium de sculpture sur granit de Laongo).

Photo 15. Laongo, an open-air sculpture museum,
(Symposium de sculpture sur granit de Laongo).

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(Symposium de sculpture sur granit de Laongo).

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(Symposium de sculpture sur granit de Laongo).

Photo 20. Laongo, an open-air sculpture museum,
(Symposium de sculpture sur granit de Laongo).

Photo 21. Laongo, an open-air sculpture museum,
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Photo 22. Laongo, an open-air sculpture museum, (Symposium de sculpture sur granit de Laongo).

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Photo 25. Laongo, an open-air sculpture museum,
(Symposium de sculpture sur granit de Laongo).

Photo 26. Laongo, an open-air sculpture museum,
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Photo 28. Laongo, an open-air sculpture museum,
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Photo 29. Laongo, an open-air sculpture museum,
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Photo 30. Laongo, an open-air sculpture museum,
(Symposium de sculpture sur granit de Laongo).

Photo 31. Laongo, an open-air sculpture museum,
(Symposium de sculpture sur granit de Laongo).

Photo 32. Laongo, an open-air sculpture museum,
(Symposium de sculpture sur granit de Laongo).

Photo 33. Waterfalls in Banfora, source: Babou Eugène IDO, avril 2019.

Photo 34. Waterfalls in Banfora, source: Tourisme au Burkina Faso (Google).

Photo 35. Waterfalls in Banfora, (Google).

Photo 36. Waterfalls in Banfora, (Google).

Photo 37. *Euplectes hordeaceus* (Linnaeus, 1758).
(<https://ebird.org>)

Photo 38. *Eurystomus glaucurus* (Müller, PLS, 1776).
(<https://ebird.org>)

Photo 39. *Corvus ruficollis* Lesson, 1831.
(<https://ebird.org>)

Photo 40. *Ploceus luteolus* (Lichtenstein, MHC, 1823).
(<https://ebird.org>)

Photo 41. *Ploceus melanocephalus*, (Linnaeus, 1758)
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Photo 43. *Ploceus vitellinus*, (Lichtenstein, MHC, 1823).
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Photo 44. *Ploceus cucullatus* (Müller, 1776).
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Photo 45. *Sporopipes frontalis* (Daudin, 1800).
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Photo 46. *Bubalomis albirostris*, (Vieillot, 1817).
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Photo 48. Elephant in the Nazinga Reserve.
(<https://discover-burkinafaso.com/choses-a-faire/>)

Photo 49. Sacred crocodile ponds of Sabou, source: ONTB.

Photo 50. A sacred crocodile in Bazoulé (Burkina Faso).

Photo 51. Habitats of Kasena, source: Faso chic.

Photo 52. Habitats of Kasena, source: ONTB.

Photo 53. Habitats of Kasena, source: Faso chic.

Photo 54. Pottery in Burkina Faso, source: ONTB.

Photo 55. Pottery in Burkina Faso, source: ONTB.

Photo 56. Pottery in Burkina Faso, source: ONTB

Photo 57. Pottery in Burkina Faso, source: ONTB.

Photo 58. Pottery in Burkina Faso, source: ONTB.

Photo 59. Pottery in Burkina Faso, source: ONTB.

Photo 60. Pottery in Burkina Faso, source : ONTB.

Photo 61. Pottery in Burkina Faso, source: ONTB.

Photo 62. Dance among the Mossi people in Burkina Faso, source: ONTB.

Photo 63. Dance among the Mossi people in Burkina Faso, source: ONTB.

Photo 64. Dance among the Bissa people in Burkina Faso, source: ONTB.

Photo 65. Dance among the Gourounsi people in Burkina Faso, source: ONTB.

Photo 66. Highlights from Burkina Faso's Festival of Masks in the city of Dédougou, (Photograph by Anthony Pappone).

Photo 67. Highlights from Burkina Faso's Festival of Masks in the city of Dédougou, (Photograph by Anthony Pappone).

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Photo 79. Highlights from Burkina Faso's Festival of Masks in the city of Dédougou, (Photograph by Anthony Pappone).

Photo 80. Rice field in the midwest of Burkina Faso.

Photo 81. Peanut field in central-western Burkina Faso.

Photo 82. Banana plantation in central-western Burkina Faso.

Photo 83. Cassava field in central-western Burkina Faso.

Photo 84. Sunflower field in central-western Burkina Faso.

Photo 85. Aerial view of the industrial gold mine in Houndé, Burkina Faso.

Photo 86. Artisanal gold mining site in Houndé, Burkina Faso.

Photo 87. Young gold miners gathered in front of artisanal gold mining sites.

Photo 88. Great Mosque-author: Issouf Sanogo, Bobo-Dioulasso.

Photo 89. Bobo-dioulasso City Hall from Burkina Faso.

Photo 90. Koudougou City Hall from Burkina Faso.

Photo 91. Koudougou, the royal palace of Issouka, a blend of tradition and modernity.

Photo 92. Place des Cinéastes, city of Ouagadougou, capital of Burkina Faso.

Photo 93. Martyrs' Roundabout (Monument to National Heroes), city of Ouagadougou.